

AVAILABILITY AND UTILIZATION OF E-LEARNING FACILITIES FOR TEACHING IN PUBLIC COLLEGES OF EDUCATION, SOUTH-WEST, NIGERIA

BY

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20965121>

Abstract

The study assessed the availability and utilization of e-learning for teaching in public Colleges of Education (COEs), South-west, Nigeria. It utilized descriptive research design of survey type. The population of the study comprised 1,987 lecturers in all the nine public COEs in South-west, Nigeria. Purposive sampling technique was used to select three states (Oyo, Ogun and Osun); and all the six public COEs in the states. Proportionate sampling technique was used to select 300 lecturers out of the 1,364 in the selected institutions. The instrument for data collection was a checklist entitled 'Availability and Utilization of E-learning Facilities for Teaching Checklist'. The instrument was subjected to validation by three experts in the field of educational management, and its reliability process was also ensured. The data collected from the reliability test conducted was analyzed using Cronbach's Alpha and reliability index of 0.84 was realized. Mean and standard deviation was used to answer research questions, while t-test was used to test hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Mean scores: 1.00 to 2.49 and 2.50 and above were adjudged 'Low' and 'High' respectively. The findings of the study revealed that there were low availability and utilization of e-learning facilities for teaching in public COEs, South-west, Nigeria. Availability. The study concluded that there were low availability and utilization of e-learning facilities (interactive boards, projectors, photograph cameras, power supply, laptops and desktops, software applications, photocopiers, internet facilities, video cameras and teleconferencing for teaching) for teaching in public COEs, South-west, Nigeria. In line with the findings, the study recommended among others that governments should ensure adequate provision of e-learning facilities for the public COEs in South-west, Nigeria, to facilitate effective e-learning method of imparting knowledge to students and enhance students' academic performance.

Keywords: *Availability, Colleges of Education, E-learning, Teaching, Utilization*

Introduction

E-learning has become an important aspect of education. It is a modern way of passing information to students, which often prevents face-to-face interaction. Okeke and Iheanacho (2019) stated that e-learning means the use of network technologies to create, foster, impart, and aid learning. It encompasses distance, face-to-face, mix, and blended delivery models that utilize electronic means of facilitating the process of teaching and learning. According to Akanbi (2020), e-learning has become an increasingly popular teaching and learning approach in higher educational institutions, due to the vast growing internet technology. E-

learning refers to the process of using technological gadgets for the process of teaching and learning. Gabriel (2021) posited that e-learning has competitive advantages and positive impacts on the teaching and learning process. Inclusion of e-learning into education, especially in Colleges of Education in Nigeria is very apt and for it to be very effective, there is need to adequately support it with the required facilities. According to Amuche (2015), e-learning facilities are the tools which encompass laptops, computers, digital cameras, video machines, computer networks, multi-media projectors or power points, television programmes, internet facilities,

telephones, e-library and databases which help to facilitate effective teaching and learning. Akpan (2018) maintained that e-learning facilities consist of vital gadgets such as multimedia, audio, networking tool, video, and other hardware and software devices which are utilized to produce, process, keep, recover and distribute information for effective teaching and learning. Owulu (2016) stated that e-learning is expected to be widely used in educational institutions, because it helps in adding more value to the teaching and learning activities. Nwana (2019) opined that e-learning is meant to transform the old methods and approaches of curriculum implementation and bring about certain changes in the behaviour of the learners. Khan et al. (2015) posited that e-learning facilities comprise cellular phones, radio, computer television, satellite systems, network, hardware and software, as well as several services and applications which are used together with them, such as distance learning and videoconferencing. Umennuihe et al. (2023) defined e-learning facilities as devices or an interrelated system of resources that is utilized in the automatic collection, storage, and management of information for the purpose of teaching and learning, to actualize the stated goals.

Ezeuwa (2014) maintained that e-learning facilities are the electronic tools which are used for the information and communication necessities in educational institutions, to facilitate seamless teaching and learning and other activities. The study conducted by Ogunjobi, et al. (2023) found that there was a significant relationship between availability of e-learning facilities and academic performance of students in Colleges of Education in Kogi State, Nigeria. Ikwuanusi et al. (2016) argued that the availability of e-learning facilities in educational institutions alone would not help improve students' academic performance, unless they are adequately utilized to enhance

quality teaching and learning process. Samuel (2021) maintained that availability of e-learning facilities is very paramount to the success of teacher education programme in Nigeria. This is necessary to keep the students abreast of how they can leverage on their utilization, to boost effective learning and consequently enhance academic performance.

Olajide (2018) stated that the significance of the availability of e-learning facilities to the improvement of teaching and learning, in addition to assisting in the realization of the established goals, cannot be over-emphasized. Lamidi (2020) asserted that insufficient availability of e-learning facilities is very common in tertiary institutions in Nigeria and it could be one of the reasons many students are not ICT-compliant. This justifies the reason Nigerian government needs to ensure adequate provision of e-learning facilities to her institutions. Samuel (2021) lamented that poor attitude of Nigerian government to education, corruption, and paucity of funds have been the challenges facing the provision of ICTs to the public institutions in Nigeria. Unless there is a paradigm shift from this ugly situation, Nigerian public institutions would continue to suffer from poor availability of e-learning facilities. The study of Hakeem (2021) found that there was not significant difference in availability of e-learning facilities for teaching in Kogi State College of Education, Kabba based on gender. The finding of the study of Hassan (2022) also revealed that male and female lecturers were not significantly different in their opinions on the availability of e-learning facilities for effective teaching and learning in Osun State College of Education, Ila-Orangun.

West and Chew (2014) asserted that utilization of e-learning helps in promoting global access to education, improvement in instructional delivery and progressive professional

enhancement of teachers, in addition to the efficient administration of school system. Umennuihe et al. (2023) opined that utilization of e-learning has become a veritable tool for actualizing speedy development in all facets of any country of the globe. Therefore, effective utilization of e-learning gadgets could have positive and maximum influence on educational enterprises. Samuel (2021) posited that the use of e-learning in education covers the implementation of overall components of ICTs in the classroom teaching and learning and this helps in achieving the stated goals. Ghavifekr and Rosdy (2015) observed that utilization of e-learning facilities affords teachers with more wide-ranging access to information needed to be prepared for students' consumption. In addition, it could provide students with the skills required to be lifelong recipient of knowledge required to meet up with their counterparts across the globe.

It is against this background that that the researchers intend to assessing the availability and utilization of e-learning facilities for teaching and learning in public Colleges of Education, South-west, Nigeria. The finding of the study of James (2022) revealed that significant difference did not exist in the perceptions of male and female lecturers on the utilization of e-learning facilities for teaching in Niger State College of Education, Minna. Monday (2024) also found in his study that there was no significant difference in the opinions of male and female lecturers on the utilization of e-learning facilities for teaching in Kwara State Colleges of Education.

Statement of the Problem

E-learning is very significant to teaching, especially at tertiary education level. However, from the information gathered from some lecturers, students, Heads of Departments and Deans in public COEs,

South-west, Nigeria, it seems that e-learning has not been well implemented, due to inadequate availability and ineffective utilization of the facilities needed to make it operate seamlessly. Lecturers in public COEs in Kwara State heavily rely on physical method of imparting knowledge to students at the expense of e-learning, despite the efforts of government in digitalizing the process of teaching and learning, to make students in COEs acquire technological skills that can make them compare with their colleagues across the globe. According to Samuel (2021), as significant as e-learning is to the enhancement of students' academic performance, it is pitiful that many public institutions in Nigeria are facing the challenge of inadequate availability and ineffective utilization of the facilities needed to ensure effective e-learning process. Akanbi (2023) asserted that tertiary institutions in Nigeria, especially the public ones, are not free from the problem of insufficiency of e-learning facilities and this could affect the utilization.

Many researchers have conducted studies related to this present study. For instance, Olajide (2018), Gabriel (2018). Akanbi (2020), Hakeem (2021), James (2022), Hassan (2022) and Monday (2024) have conducted various studies which are important to this study. However, none of the afore-mentioned studies focused on assessing the availability and utilization of e-learning facilities for teaching in public COEs, South-west, Nigeria. Therefore, this formed the academic lacuna which this study filled.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to examine the availability and utilization of e-learning facilities for teaching in public COEs, South-west, Nigeria. Specifically, the study:

- i. determined the availability of e-learning facilities for teaching in public COEs, South-west, Nigeria;
- ii. examined the utilization of e-learning facilities for teaching in public COEs, South-west, Nigeria;
- iii. investigated the availability of e-learning for teaching in public COEs, South-west, Nigeria based on gender; and
- iv. determined the utilization of e-learning facilities for teaching in public COEs, South-west, Nigeria based on gender.

Research Questions

- i. What is the availability of e-learning facilities for teaching in public COEs, South-west, Nigeria?
- ii. What is the utilization of e-learning facilities for teaching in public COEs, South-west, Nigeria?

Research Hypotheses

Ho₁: There is no significant difference in the availability of e-learning facilities for teaching in public COEs, South-west, Nigeria based on gender.

Ho₂: There is no significant difference in the utilization of e-learning facilities for teaching in public COEs, South-west, Nigeria based on gender.

Research Methods

Descriptive research design of survey type was used for the study. The population of the study comprised 1,987 lecturers in all the nine public COEs in South-west, Nigeria. There were six states in South-western Nigeria. Purposive sampling technique was used to select their states (Oyo, Ogun and Osun) which had both federal and state COEs; and all the six public COEs in the states. Proportionate sampling technique was used to select 26 lecturers out of the 117 in Federal College of Education, Iwo, Osun State; 53 lecturers out of the 243 in Federal College of Education,

Abeokuta, Ogun State; 124 lecturers out of the 564 in Federal College of Education (Special), Oyo, Oyo State; 33 lecturers out of the 148 in Osun State College of Education, Ila-Orangun; 23 lecturers out of the 103 in Oyo State College of Education, Lanalate; and 41 lecturers out of the 189 in Sikiru Adetona College of Education Science and Technology, Omu-Ajose, Ogun State, making 300 lecturers out of the 1,364 in the six institutions, using Krejcie and Morgan (1970) table for sample size determination.

Researcher-designed instrument titled 'Availability and Utilization of E-Learning Facilities for Teaching Questionnaire' (AUELFTQ) was utilized to collect data. Response options of Highly Available (HA), Available (A), Fairly Available (FA) and Not Available (NA); and Highly Utilized (HU), Utilized (U), Fairly Utilized (U) and Not Utilized (NU) that were rated 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively were used for scoring items on the questionnaire. The draft of the questionnaire was presented to three experts for validation. Thirty copies of the instrument were administered to 30 lecturers outside the selected COEs.

Cronbach's Alpha was used to analyses the data gathered and reliability index of 0.84 was realized. This means that the instrument was reliable for use. The researchers and three research assistants collected data for the study. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer research questions, while t-test was used to test hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Mean scores: 1.00 to 2.49 and 2.50 and above were adjudged 'Low' and 'High' respectively.

Results

Research Question 1: What is the availability of e-learning facilities for teaching in public COEs, South-west, Nigeria?

Table 2

Availability of E-learning Facilities for Teaching in Public COEs, South-west, Nigeria

S/N	Items	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
1.	Interactive boards	1.56	.34	Low
2.	Projectors	2.39	.78	Low
3.	Photograph cameras	2.32	.72	Low
4.	Power supply	2.00	.68	Low
5.	Laptops and desktops	2.34	.45	Low
6.	Software applications	2.19	.50	Low
7.	Photocopiers	2.37	.64	Low
8.	Internet facilities	2.41	.89	Low
9.	Video cameras	2.00	.68	Low
10.	Teleconferencing	1.82	.33	Low

\bar{X} : 1.00-2.49 = Low; 2.50-4.00 = High

Table 2 shows the availability of e-learning facilities for teaching in public COEs, South-west, Nigeria. As revealed in the table, the mean scores of items 1-10 (interactive boards, projectors, photograph cameras, power supply, laptops and desktops, software applications, photocopiers, internet facilities, video cameras and teleconferencing) were

less than 2.50. Therefore, the decisions taken on them was low.

Research Question 1: What is the utilization of e-learning facilities for teaching in public COEs, South-west, Nigeria?

Table 3

Utilization of E-learning Facilities for Teaching in public COEs, South-west, Nigeria

S/N	Items	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
1.	Interactive boards	1.98	.43	Low
2.	Projectors	2.22	.69	Low
3.	Photograph cameras	2.13	.58	Low
4.	Power Supply	2.08	.51	Low
5.	Laptops and desktops	2.39	.78	Low
6.	Software applications	2.39	.78	Low

7.	Photocopiers	2.17	.60	Low
8.	Internet facilities	2.34	.75	Low
9.	Video cameras	2.10	.54	Low
10.	Teleconferencing	1.97	.40	Low

\bar{X} : 1.00-2.49 = Low; 2.50-4.00 = High

Table 3 shows the utilization of e-learning facilities for teaching and learning in public COEs, South-west, Nigeria. As shown in the table, the mean scores of items 1-10 (interactive boards, projectors, photograph cameras, power supply, laptops and desktops, software applications, photocopiers, internet facilities, video cameras and teleconferencing)

were less than 2.50. Hence, the decisions taken on them was ‘low.’

Ho₁: There is no significant difference in the availability of e-learning facilities for teaching in public COEs, South-west, Nigeria based on gender.

Table 4

Difference in the Availability of E-learning Facilities for Teaching Based on Gender

Gender	N	\bar{X}	SD	t-cal.	p-value	Decision
Male	101	2.01	.045			
				2.56	.068	Ho ₁ Accepted
Female	67	2.27	.075			

Table 4 shows the calculated t-value (2.56), and the p-value (0.68) which is greater than 0.05 level of significance. Based on this, null hypothesis one was accepted. This shows that there was no significant difference in the availability of e-learning facilities for teaching

in public COEs, South-west, Nigeria based on gender.

Ho₂: There is no significant difference in the utilization of e-learning facilities for teaching in public COEs, South-west, Nigeria based on gender.

Table 5

Difference in the Utilization of E-learning Facilities for Teaching Based on Gender

Gender	N	\bar{X}	SD	t-cal.	p-value	Decision
Male	101	2.09	.050			
				2.49	Ho ₂ .075	Accepted

Table 5 shows the calculated t-value (2.49) and the p-value (0.75) which is greater than 0.05 level of significance. Hence, null hypothesis two was accepted. This depicts that there was

Discussions

The findings of the study revealed that the availability of e-learning facilities: interactive boards, projectors, photograph cameras, power supply, laptops and desktops, software applications, photocopiers, internet facilities, video cameras and teleconferencing for teaching was low in public COEs, South-west, Nigeria. This finding agrees with the finding of James (2022) which revealed that the level of availability of laptops, desktops, flash drives, video cameras, photographs cameras, C.D. drives, power supply and projectors for e-learning was low in Niger State College of Education, Minna. This finding is in tandem with the finding of Hakeem (2021) that the level of e-learning facilities availability was low in Kogi State College of Education, Kabba.

The findings of the study showed that the utilization of interactive boards, projectors, photograph cameras, power supply, laptops and desktops, software applications, photocopiers, internet facilities, video cameras and teleconferencing for teaching was low in public COEs, South-west, Nigeria. This finding supports the findings of Monday (2024) that the utilization of e-learning facilities such as computers, internet service, social media platform, video cameras, photo cameras, interactive boards, power supply and teleconferencing was low in Kwara State Colleges of Education. This finding is in consonance with the finding of Hassan (2022) that the level of utilisation of e-learning facilities for leaching and learning was low in Osun State College of Education, Ila-Orangun.

no significant difference in the utilization of e-learning facilities for teaching in public COEs, South-west, Nigeria based on gender.

The findings of the study revealed that there was no significant difference in the availability of e-learning facilities for teaching in public COEs, South-west, Nigeria based on gender. This means that male and female lecturers were not significantly different in their opinions on the availability of e-learning facilities for teaching. This finding corroborates the finding of James (2022) which revealed that there was no significant difference in the opinions of male and female lecturers on the availability of e-learning facilities for teaching in Niger State College of Education, Minna. This finding supports the finding of Hakeem (2021) significant difference does not exist in the availability of e-learning facilities for teaching in Kogi State College of Education, Kabba.

As found by the outcome of the study, there was no significant difference in the utilization of e-learning facilities for teaching in public COEs, South-west, Nigeria based on gender. This means that male and female lecturers were of similar opinions on the utilization of e-learning facilities for teaching. This agrees with the findings of Monday (2024) that there was no significant difference in the opinions of male and female lecturers on the unitization of e-learning facilities for teaching in Kwara State Colleges of Education. This finding supports the finding of Hassan (2022) that there was no significant difference in the opinions of male and female lecturers in the utilisation of e-learning facilities for leaching and learning in Osun State College of Education, Ila-Orangun.

Conclusion

The study concluded that there was low availability and utilization of e-learning facilities (interactive boards, projectors, photograph cameras, power supply, laptops and desktops, software applications, photocopiers, internet facilities, video cameras and teleconferencing for teaching) for teaching in public COEs, South-west, Nigeria. Also, opinions of male and female lecturers were not significantly different on the availability and the utilization of e-learning facilities for teaching in the institutions.

Recommendations

The study recommended that:

- i. Governments should ensure adequate provision of e-learning facilities for the public COEs in South-west, Nigeria, to facilitate effective e-learning method of imparting knowledge to students and enhance students' academic performance;
- ii. the managements of the institutions should make and also keenly implement a policy that would mandate lecturers to make use of e-learning facilities for teaching, to facilitate effective learning by students.

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